

Effect of Composition on Solution Properties of Styrene-Ethylacrylate Copolymers*

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Poly(styrene-co-ethylacrylate) of composition 1 : 1 (PSEA) and 4 : 1 (UPSEA) were prepared by bulk polymerization and fractionated using methyl ethyl ketone as solvent and methanol as non-solvent at 30°. The composition and microstructure were determined by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance. Short range interactions between chain units of random copolymers in solution may be influenced by the composition and by the distribution of sequence lengths of monomer units in the copolymer. Steric factors were obtained for random copolymers of styrene and ethyl acrylate with different compositions from the relation between the limiting viscosity number and molecular weight.

The Mark-Houwink relationships, $[\eta] = 1.29 \times 10^{-2} \bar{M}_w^{0.70}$ for PEAS and $[\eta] = 1.25 \times 10^{-2} \bar{M}_w^{0.69}$ for UPEAS in methyl ethyl ketone at 35° were established. With Stockmayer-Fixman expression, these correlations become respectively for PSEA and UPSEA :

$$[\eta] = 10.73 \times 10^{-2} \bar{M}_w^{-1/2} + 0.726 \times 10^{-4} \bar{M}_w$$

$$[\eta] = 8.89 \times 10^{-2} \bar{M}_w^{1/2} + 0.100 \times 10^{-3} \bar{M}_w$$

From the unperturbed mean square end-to-end distance (\bar{r}_0^2) calculated from the first term of Stockmayer-Fixman expression and from \bar{r}_{of}^2 calculated by assuming the complete free rotation, the steric factor, $\sigma = \bar{r}_0^2 / \bar{r}_{of}^2$ was found to be 2.34 for PSEA and 2.24 for UPSEA. These values are greater than those for polystyrene (2.22) and Poly(ethyl acrylate) (2.22). It may be concluded that the dimensions of the copolymer are influenced by the electrostatic interaction between carboxy ethyl groups of ethyl acrylate and phenyl groups of styrene.

The steric factors, $\sigma = \bar{r}_0^2 / \bar{r}_{of}^2$ have been calculated for styrene-acrylonitrile copolymers of different compositions and for methyl methacrylate-acrylonitrile copolymers by Shimura^{1,2} who concluded that the dimensions of random copolymers of styrene and acrylonitrile in solution were not significantly influenced by the composition¹ whereas the dimensions of the copolymer of methyl methacrylate and acrylonitrile were influenced by the composition². It was observed that the second virial coefficients of copolymers were found to be larger than those for the constituent homopolymers³. In the present work, the effect of composition on short range and long range interactions for styrene-ethyl acrylate copolymer was examined experimentally.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solvents : Methyl ethyl ketone (BDH, LR) and methanol (BDH, LR) were purified according to standard procedures⁴.

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Monomers: Styrene (Merck, Germany), ethyl acrylate (Chem. pure India) were washed thrice with sodium hydroxide (5%) followed by distilled water, dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 finally and distilled under reduced pressure (< 10 mm of Hg) in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

Copolymerization: Bulk copolymerization of styrene and ethyl acrylate monomers [styrene (56.6 ml) and ethyl acrylate (106.8 ml) calculated from the respective reactivity ratios⁵ $r_1 = 0.80$ and $r_2 = 0.20$ for getting 1 : 1 copolymer and styrene (75.5 ml) and ethyl acrylate (35.6 ml) calculated from the reactivity ratios⁵ for getting 4 : 1 copolymer] was carried out with azobisisobutyronitrile (0.1 gm) as initiator under deaerated conditions to conversion $< 10\%$ at $70^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The reaction mixture was taken up in methyl ethyl ketone (solvent) and precipitated with methanol (non-solvent). The polymers were purified by dissolution in solvent and reprecipitation by non-solvent. The polymer was fractionated by fractional precipitation technique using methyl ethyl ketone as solvent and methanol as non-solvent at 30° .

Osmotic pressure: An osmometer (Pinner-Stabin; Colchester Instruments, Ltd., U.K.) filled with preconditioned gel cellulose (PECEL 600) membranes was employed to measure the osmotic pressure of PSEA sample in methyl ethyl ketone at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The numbers of average molecular weight were obtained from the plot of $(\pi/c)^{\frac{1}{3}}$ vs. c .

Viscosity: Viscosities of pure solvent (methyl ethyl ketone) and filtered polymer solutions (six concentration in the range 2×10^{-3} to 5×10^{-4} gm/ml) were measured in suspended level dilution viscometer (Colchester Instruments, Ltd., U.K.) at $35^\circ \pm 0.01^\circ$. The kinetic energy correction though small ($< 1\%$) was applied to the measured flow time. The limiting viscosity numbers were obtained as the mean of three $[\eta]$ s obtained from equations :

$$\eta_{sp/c} = [\eta] + k_1[\eta]^2C \text{ due to Huggins}^6$$

$$(\ln \eta_{rel})/c = [\eta] - k_2[\eta]^2c \text{ due to Kraemer}^7$$

$$\eta_{sp/c} = [\eta] + k_3[\eta]\eta_{sp} \text{ due to Schulz Blaschke}^8.$$

Light scattering: Light scattering measurements of PSEA and UPSEA in methyl ethyl ketone were carried out at $35^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$ in a Brice-Phoenix universal light scattering photometer⁹ (series 1999-12, Phoenix Precision Instruments Company, Philadelphia) with the use of unpolarized light $\lambda = 4356 \text{ \AA}$ at various angles. The refractive index increments (dn/dc) of PSEA (0.169 ± 0.004) and UPSEA (0.201 ± 0.002) in methyl ethyl ketone were measured in a differential refractometer¹⁰ (Brice-Phoenix No. 1974; Phoenix Precision Instrument Company, Philadelphia). The light scattering data were treated according to the method of Zimm¹¹. The weight average molecular weight \bar{M}_w , the z average radius of gyration $(\bar{S}^2)_z$ and the second virial coefficient were calculated from the plots of Kc/R_θ vs $\text{Sin}^2 \theta/2 + 100c$. $(\bar{S}^2)_z$ was then converted to $(\bar{S}^2)_w$ by the equation¹²:

$$(\bar{S}^2)_w = (\bar{S}^2)_z (h+1)/(h+2+\beta)$$

where $h = [(M_w/M_n) - 1]^{-1}$ and $\beta = (2a - 1)/3$ where 'a' is exponent in the Mark-Houwink equation. The polydispersity M_w/M_n of PSEA was calculated from the ratio of molecular weight obtained by light scattering and osmometry and found to be 1.18.

Analyses of copolymer: NMR spectra of copolymers were taken in CDCl_3 solution (10%) using a (varian A-60) spectrometer working at 60 MH_z (Courtesy—Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Bombay) with the tetramethyl silane as an internal standard for the estimation of composition and microstructure of copolymer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(a) *Composition of the copolymer*: The basis for the NMR curve analysis method lies in the fact that the aromatic resonance of polystyrene consists of two well resolved peaks with an integrated intensity ratio of 3 to 2. Bovey, Tiers and Fillipovich¹³ attributed the resonance at 3.0 τ to the para and the two meta protons and that at 3.5 τ to the two ortho protons. Both peaks are shifted upfield from the aromatic resonance of single styrene unit or a model compound such as toluene (2.86 τ) but the ortho proton experiences the greater shift (3.5 τ). These chemical shifts arise from a "ring current" effect and an overlapping of the phenyl rings of neighbouring styrene units¹³. From the relative intensity of shifted ortho proton resonance compared to total styrene aromatic resonance, the NMR 'block styrene' value can be determined in copolymers. Mochel and Claxton¹⁴ showed that in *n*-BuLi initiated styrene—butadiene copolymers quite a quantitative distinction can be made between short blocks, which contain two to three styrene units and long blocks, which include styrene sequences four units and longer. The resonance attributed to long blocks appears as a separate peak at 3.5 τ at the start of formation of styrene sequences longer than three units¹⁴. The NMR spectra of poly (styrene-co-ethyl acrylate) of 1 : 1, 4 : 1, 1 : 4 compositions were recorded in CDCl_3 . The NMR spectra of PSEA (1 : 1) in Fig. 1 showed the phenyl proton peak at 2.84 τ with a shoulder at 3.175 τ , $-\text{OCH}_2$ proton peak at 6.15 τ , $-\text{CH}-\text{CH}_2$ protons of styrene and ethyl acrylate between 8.35 τ –8.9 τ . The relative areas of the peaks of phenyl proton and $-\text{OCH}_2$ proton indicated the ratio of phenyl group to $-\text{OCH}_2$ group to be 1 : 1 and therefore the composition of the copolymer with respect to ethyl acrylate

Fig. 1. NMR Spectrum of Poly(styrene-co-ethylacrylate) 1 : 1

and styrene was 1 : 1. The shoulder in the phenyl proton peak at 3.17 τ indicated the presence of styrene blocks (< 5 units) in the copolymer. The NMR spectra of 4 : 1 composition showed the phenyl proton peak at 2.85 τ with a shoulder at 3.25 τ and the $-\text{OCH}_2$ proton peak at 6.20 τ . The relative areas however indicated the lower percentage of styrene (70%) in the copolymer than that expected from kinetics (80%). The phenyl proton peak showed a separate peak (or a shoulder) at 3.25 τ indicating the presence of more than 10 units of styrene as blocks in the copolymer. The NMR spectra of poly (styrene-co-ethyl acrylate) of 1 : 4 composition showed the phenyl proton peak at 2.81 τ without a shoulder and the $-\text{OCH}_2$ proton peak at 5.98 τ . The presence of single phenyl proton peak without a shoulder indicates the absence of styrene blocks¹³ which is expected from kinetics also.

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log_{10} [\eta]$ vs $\log_{10} \bar{M}_w$ A : PSEA in methyl ethyl ketone.
 B : UPSEA in methyl ethyl ketone.
 Poly (Ethyl Acrylate-co-styrene) 1 : 1, 1 : 4

The solution properties of fractionated poly(styrene-co-ethyl acrylate) 1 : 1 (eight samples designated as PSEA₁ - PSEA₈) as well as poly(styrene-co-ethyl acrylate) 4 : 1 (five samples designated as UPSEA₁ - UPSEA₅) in methyl ethyl ketone were investigated by light scattering and viscometry.

Mark-Houwink equations : From the log-log plots of limiting viscosity number $[\eta]$ against molecular weight for PSEA and UPSEA (Fig. 2, Table 1 and 2) the following Mark-Houwink relationships were established in methyl ethyl ketone at 35° respectively :

$$[\eta] = 1.29 \times 10^{-2} \bar{M}_w^{0.70}$$

$$[\eta] = 1.25 \times 10^{-2} \bar{M}_w^{0.69}$$

TABLE 1

Parameters obtained from light scattering and viscosity

Polymer : poly (styrene-co-ethylacrylate) 1 : 1

Solvent : Methyl ethyl ketone

 $\lambda = 4356 \text{ \AA}$

Temp : 35°

 $dn/dc = 0.169 \pm 0.004$ $h = 4; a = 0.69$

Polymer	$\bar{M}_w \cdot 10^{-5}$	$[\eta]$ ml.gm ⁻¹	k'	$(\bar{r}^2)_{w}^{\dagger}$ Å	$A_2 \cdot 10^4$ cc.mole.gm ⁻²	$\Phi \cdot 10^{-23}$
PSEA ₁	2.964	78.5	0.32	771	1.29	0.51
PSEA ₂	3.600	85.5	0.30	814	1.27	0.57
PSEA ₃	3.925	95.5	0.42	898	1.19	0.52
PSEA ₄	4.139	100.0	0.29	912	1.06	0.56
PSEA ₅	4.812	112.7	0.32	991	—	0.56
PSEA ₆	5.297	120.0	0.33	1070	1.17	0.53
PSEA ₇	8.149	166.9	0.32	1327	0.94	0.58
PSEA ₈	15.840	242.0	0.34	1877	0.75	0.58

TABLE 2

Parameters obtained from light scattering and viscosity

Polymer : poly (Styrene-co-ethylacrylate) 4 : 1

Solvent : Methyl ethyl ketone

 $\lambda = 4356 \text{ \AA};$ $dn/dc = 0.201 \pm 0.002$ Temp = 35°; $h = 4$

Polymer	$\bar{M}_w \cdot 10^{-5}$	$[\eta]$ ml.gm ⁻¹	k'	$(\bar{r}^2)_{w}^{\dagger}$ Å	$A_2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ cc.mole.gm ⁻²	$\Phi \cdot 10^{-23}$
UPSEA ₁	1.854	55.55	0.22	795	2.98	0.20
UPSEA ₂	2.252	66.21	0.19	810	2.95	0.28
UPSEA ₃	2.483	69.79	0.38	864	2.28	0.34
UPSEA ₄	2.632	72.12	0.42	893	2.10	0.28
UPSEA ₅	3.535	87.75	0.29	1040	2.12	0.28

From the Mark-Houwink equations established for polystyrene⁵ and poly(ethyl acrylate)¹⁵ in methyl ethyl ketone it was observed that for the same molecular weight, PSEA and UPSEA gives larger limiting viscosity numbers than that for polystyrene and lower values than that for poly(ethyl acrylate). PSEA and UPSEA chains therefore appear to be more expanded beyond the free rotation dimensions than that of polystyrene and less than that of poly(ethyl acrylate) in methyl ethyl ketone. Further, the composition of the copolymer does not have marked influence on the limiting viscosity number in the molecular weight range studied.

Molecular dimension—Molecular weight relationships : From log-log plots of $(\bar{r}^2)_{w}^{\dagger}$ vs \bar{M}_w the following relationships were established in methyl ethyl ketone (Fig 3, Table 1 and 2) for PSEA and UPSEA respectively :

$$(\bar{r}^2)_{w}^{\dagger} = 0.83 \bar{M}_w^{0.54}$$

$$(\bar{r}^2)_{w}^{\dagger} = 1.419 \bar{M}_w^{0.52}$$

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log_{10}(\bar{r}^2)^{1/2}_w$ vs $\log_{10}\bar{M}_w$ A: PSEA in methyl ethyl ketone.
 B: UPSEA in methyl ethyl ketone.
 Log (M_w) vs Log $(\bar{r}^2)^{1/2}_w$

The value of the exponent (i.e., > 0.50) indicates that methyl ethyl ketone is a good solvent for PSEA and UPSEA¹⁶. Further for the same molecular weight, the dimension of UPSEA was found to be greater than that of PSEA, indicating the effect of composition on mean square end-to-end distance.

Second virial co-efficient: From values of second virial coefficients given in Table 1 and 2 it is clear that there is a tendency for magnitude of A_2 to decrease as the size of the molecule increases as has been observed on number of homopolymers^{17,18}.

Stockmayer-Fixman expression: Number of graphical procedures are available for the determination of unperturbed mean square end-to-end distances of polymer molecules from intrinsic viscosity and molecular weight measurements in non-ideal solvents¹⁹⁻²⁶. Among the methods employed for obtaining K_θ from intrinsic viscosity/molecular weight data, the graphical procedures described by Flory-Fox, and Schaefgen (F-F-S)¹⁹, Kurata and Stockmayer (K-S)²⁰, Stockmayer-Fixman (S-F)²⁰ and Ptitsyn-Inagaki (P-I)²⁴ methods are generally employed. Chinai *et al.*¹⁶ and Kurata *et al.*²⁰ found that F-F-S method to be inadequate in good solvents²⁷. The K-S and S-F methods were observed to give same K_θ value and were equally applicable in good and poor solvents²⁷. Further, Cowie²³ has shown that S-F method gives correct K_θ values (equal to those obtained in θ solvents) when the molecular weight of the fractions are $< 1 \times 10^6$ and the exponent in the Mark-Houwink equation is < 0.70 . These considerations hold good for PSEA and UPSEA and therefore Stockmayer-Fixman relation:

$$[\eta] = \Phi_0 A^3 M^{1/2} + 0.51 B \Phi_0 M$$

(where $A = (\overline{r_0^2}/M)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, Φ_0 is universal parameter with a value of 2.86×10^{23} , $\overline{r_0^2}$ is the unperturbed mean square end-to-end distance and B is a parameter representing interactions between the polymer and solvent) was employed. From this relation we can obtain some knowledge about the conformations of PSEA and UPSEA copolymers. With the method of least squares, the following relationships were obtained :

$$[\eta] = 8.89 \times 10^{-2} M^{\frac{1}{2}} + 0.1003 \times 10^{-3} \overline{M} \text{ for UPSEA}$$

$$[\eta] = 10.73 \times 10^{-2} M^{\frac{1}{2}} + 0.7268 \times 10^{-4} \overline{M} \text{ for PSEA}$$

Steric factor : To calculate the steric factor, we must assume that the mean square end-to-end distance divided by the degree of polymerization ($\overline{r_{of}^2}/P$) is independent of the substituent on the main chain in which the internal rotation about the carbon-carbon bond of the backbone of the chain is assumed to be completely free²⁸. The ratio ($\overline{r_{of}^2}/M$) can be calculated from (r_{of}^2/P) and the molecular weight of the copolymer. For PSEA copolymer, (r_{of}^2/M)^{1/2} is 312×10^{-11} and for UPSEA it is 302×10^{-11} . On the other hand we obtain values ($\overline{r_0^2}/M$)^{1/2} = 723×10^{-11} and 677×10^{-11} for PSEA and UPSEA respectively from the intercept of the plot of $[\eta]/M^{\frac{1}{2}}$ vs $M^{\frac{1}{2}}$ (Fig. 4). The ratio of these quantities gives the steric factor, σ , which is the measure of hindrance to free rotation about the carbon-carbon bond. The steric factors for PSEA and UPSEA were found to be 2.35 and 2.24 respectively. The greater values for copolymers compared to those for constituent homopolymers, polystyrene

Fig. 4. Stockmayer—Fixman graph for K_0 evaluation.
Poly(ethyl acrylate-co-styrene) 1 : 1, 1 : 4

($\sigma = 2.22$) and poly(ethyl acrylate) ($\sigma = 2.22$) signify that the copolymer is more expanded over those of the homopolymers due to comonomer repulsions similar to those encountered in the polymer incompatibility²⁹. The steric factor, for poly(methyl acrylate-co-styrene)³³

(2.46) was found to be greater than those for polystyrene (2.22) and poly(methyl acrylate)³³ (2.05) and that for poly(butyl acrylate-co-styrene)³⁴ was also found to be greater than those for polystyrene (2.22) and poly(butyl acrylate)³⁴ (2.58). Hence it may be concluded that the copolymers were stiff coils compared to the constituent homopolymers.

Calculation of rms end-to-end distance : Values of end-to-end distance were calculated from Debye-Bueche theory³⁰ (equivalent sphere model) and Kirkwood-Riseman theory³¹ (partially permeable statistical chain model) to attempt to visualize the shape of the molecular chain in solution. It was observed that $(\bar{r}^2)^{1/2}_w$ measured by light scattering was 1.6 to 1.8 times greater than those calculated from the theories (Table 3). Even though good agreement between theoretical and experimental values has been observed for a number

TABLE 3

Comparison of root mean square end-to-end distance from hydrodynamic theory and experiment

Polymer : poly (styrene-co-ethyl acrylate) 1 : 1
 $a = 0.69$; $\bar{\phi}(\sigma) = 1.45$; $x'F(x') = 0.775$ Solvent : methyl ethyl ketone
 Temp : 35°.

Polymer	$M\delta \cdot 10^{-5}$	D-B	$(\bar{r}^2)^{1/2}_w$ Å K-R	Exptl.
PSEA ₁	2.964	352	483	771
PSEA ₂	3.600	382	530	814
PSEA ₃	3.925	412	566	898
PSEA ₄	4.139	426	585	912
PSEA ₅	4.812	466	640	991
PSEA ₆	5.297	492	675	1070
PSEA ₇	8.149	633	869	1327
PSEA ₈	15.840	895	1227	1877

D-B = Debye-Bueche

K-R = Kirkwood-Riseman

of methacrylate polymers^{16,17} and methacrylate copolymers with styrene³², higher experimental values than the theoretical values have been observed for poly(methyl acrylate)³³, poly(ethyl acrylate)³⁴, poly(butyl acrylate)³⁴, poly(methyl acrylate-co-styrene)³³, poly(ethyl acrylate-co-styrene) and poly(butyl acrylate-co-styrene)³⁴.

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